

Agroforestry business environment

- Agroforestry is a sustainable land management practice able to deliver ecosystem services in different environments, providing adequate implementation and management.
- Agroforestry transition should be moved within an adequate business environment framework build upon adequate (i) Institutional Development, (ii) technology and knowledge, (iii) funding, (iv) resource and infrastructure, (v) training and education, (vi) market structure, and (vii) consumer agency
- Agroforestry transition is promoted by adequate short and long term business models within a specific business environment framework

Institutional development

Agroforestry institutional development has been steadily improved if the previous CAP are considered and formally involved as part of different strategies linked to agroecology. However, the uptake of agroforestry is still very low. Fostering monitoring, advisory systems, training and support is essential to enhance the farmers agroforestry uptake. Especially important is the connection between the agroecosystem and the agri-business making easy the understanding of farmers in terms of economic feasibility and policy makers in terms of ecosystem services benefits. The Development of rules, regulations and policy instruments that promote or not prevent from Agroforestry implementation is essential to foster agroforestry transition across Europe. The promotion of policy, regulation and rules coherence integration and the reduction of bureaucracy from different ministries would help to fulfil social, environmental and economic benefits.

Technology, knowledge, training and education

Technology and knowledge is well developed at research level to understand the main principles supporting agroforestry. However, technology and knowledge adaptation to real conditions considering the highly biodiverse set of European environments is still poorly developed. Agroforestry advisory services are poorly developed with regard to hard and soft skills that are initially tackled by the AF knowledge platform..

Funding, resources and infrastructure

The CAP, as the most relevant EU policy, is promoting agroforestry at different levels, but the uptake by farmers is still small due to the lack of connectivity along the agrifood sector. Moreover, Agroforestry is usually linked to marginal lands where infrastructures and resources are depleted enhancing land abandonment and ageing of the population.

Market structure and consumer agency

There are several good examples of agroforestry labelled products across Europe, however, the label is not yet properly organized at global level. Usually, agroforestry is linked to short value chains that are highly biodiverse. Moreover, the analysis of the CAP reflects that in general short value chains, food quality, bioeconomy and circular economy interventions are very poorly activated in spite of agroforestry proved biodiversity, ecosystem services delivery and carbon mitigation promotion as well as forest resilience increase. Agroforestry is well perceived by the farmers as a way to promote sustainability, but this concept of linking the food to the use and

management of the territory at local bases is not fully understood. Agroforestry is a practice linked to organic and agroecological farming systems as part of the tools they use to optimize the use of the resources. Some agroforestry products such as the “Iberian jamón” is associated with a type of sustainable system called Dehesa linked to extensive farming systems, but, it is better understood as a product quality than in the agroforestry concept by the consumer.

MAIN CONCLUSIONS

- **Fostering institutional dialogue to develop better targeted policies reducing bureaucracy**
- **Local adaptation of agroforestry research knowledge and advisory systems should be promoted**
- **Agroforestry is well adapted to marginal lands where resources and infrastructures are scarce, enhancing land abandonment**
- **Agroforestry fits well in short and diverse value chain enhancing market and climate change resilience, but it is not recognized as such by consumers**

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